

Issues of literary influence in modern Uzbek literature

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Literary influence, according to experts, appears on the basis of the following factors: 1) through social, cultural, literary relations between two or more nations; 2) on the basis of kinship between literatures, certain genetic connection, belonging to a certain ethnic group (for example, the literature of genetic nations); 3) the literary influence can be large-scale and multi-stage, forming a whole literary period (e.g., J.J.Rousseau and J.G.Byron's literary influence to A.Pushkin, M.Lermontov, L.Tolstoys' works); 4) a type of literary communication between writers. Another author's use of a plot, image, popular motifs or artistic ideas, etc.¹

In the Dictionary of Literary Studies, the term "literary influence" is defined as "(from Russian: литературное влияние) - a phenomenon that exists naturally and legally in the literary process, and is of significant importance in the development of artistic thinking. Literary influence occurs as a result of interaction of literary-artistic events regardless of time and space. Therefore, literary influence is observed within the framework of one national literature or inter-literature relations, literature of the same period or literature of different periods. Accordingly, the scope and level of literary influence are different (general and personal), and they depend on a number of factors.²

¹ <https://literaturologiya.academic.ru>

² Куронов Д. ва бошқалар. Адабиётшунослик луғати. – Тошкент: Академнашр, 2010. – Б. 16.

The following comments of S.Meli, doctor of philological sciences, emphasize that typology and literary influence are legally related, cultural phenomena with a real basis, and help us to determine the limits of logical precision of literary influence: "Literary influence is the basis of typology has its own special appearance, which also occurs in the form of certain similarities and commonalities in artistic phenomena. The difference between literary influence and typology is that the creative or artistic work influencing one another must be reasonable in terms of time, space and logic. Let's say, it is impossible to talk about Dante's influence on Yusuf Khos Khajib's work, because the author of "Kutadgu Bilig" lived two centuries before Dante. The opposite is also impossible, because it is extremely unlikely that Dante was familiar with "Kutadgu Bilig".³

It is possible to cite many more scientific conclusions from Uzbek and world literary studies that are close to the above or have certain differences. At the moment, all of them emphasize that the activity of one nation's literature towards other nations, the avant-garde in artistic thinking will be an important tool for literary influence. Historical contemporaneity, national, ethnic proximity, geographical boundaries do not play a major role in this. Literature is such an aesthetic, mysterious process that it can easily overcome the walls of time, space, culture, religion, and belief, and can easily influence other literatures, the work of a specific writer, and make a great contribution to the development of art.

It is natural that we can easily observe this situation in the long and recent history of Uzbek literature. It goes without saying that as a result of the influence of Arabic and Persian literature on Uzbek classical literature, great changes took place in Uzbek classical poetry and classical prose. The fact that "Khamisa"

³ Милиев Сувонқул (Сувон Мели). Глобал илмий-бадий талқин поэтикаси. Филология фанлари доктори (DSc.) диссертацияси. – Тошкент, 2019. – Б. 110

originally written in Persian was continued in Turkish by Alisher Navoi, and the high status of Khamsa is emphasized by all Navoi scholars. Updates in Turkish, Azerbaijani, and Persian literature, which continued epic traditions under the influence of Navoi, consistent continuation of Navoi's traditions in the literary environment of Khorezm and Kokan is a clear proof of our opinion. The influence of Abdulkadir Bedil and Muhammad Fuzuli on Uzbek literature since the 17th century also shows that this process is an important aesthetic phenomenon.

The new poetic genres that entered Uzbek literature in the 20th century are a great proof that the modern world poetry was influenced by them. They themselves admit that they are creatively influenced by Turkish, Tatar, Azerbaijani, Arabic, Persian, Russian new literature. Dramaturgy, which is completely new for Uzbek literature, is also the result of literary influence. In his theoretical research entitled "Drama Genre", the philological sciences Uzoq Djourakulov proved that this phenomenon has social, cultural-historical and artistic foundations.

It is denied that there are epic traditions of Turkish, Arabic, French, English, Russian literature in the works of A.Qadiri, A.Cholpon, Oybek, G.Gulom, A.Qahhor in the Uzbek prose of the beginning and middle of the 20th century. cannot be reached. It is known that A.Qadiri and A.Cholpon were among the first to create Uzbek novels. We find notes in the scientific literature that both of them know the Russian language perfectly. So, they got acquainted with European prose and Russian literature through this intermediate language. At the same time, the fact that they know Turkish and Arabic languages shows that they are also familiar with the modern literature of the East. The next generation got to know world literature mainly through Russian translations. There are characters of Russian nationality in the prose of Oybek and G.Ghulom. A.Qahhor himself admits that he was directly influenced by the classics of Russian literature. For example, he

mentions A.P.Chekhov as his mentor. This tradition continued consistently in the works of O.Yaqubov, P.Kadirov, A. Mukhtar, of course. In particular, it is known that A. Mukhtar perfected the characters of his novels under the influence of L. Tolstoy's prose, and even included the character of L. Tolstoy in the novel "Chinor". O.Yaqubov introduced the Uzbek version of the image of "chudak(чудак)", which is consistently found in the prose of V. Shukshin, etc.

There is no doubt that Russian literature and world literature through Russian translations had a unique influence on the works of Sh.Kholmirzaev, O.Umarbekov, U.Nazarov, and O.Mukhtar. City man, village man, outcast, small man images, sentimental and romantic images are new images that appeared directly as a result of reading the works of L.Tolstoy, F.Dostoevsky, M.Sholokhov, V.Shukshin, V.Rasputin

In the 1980s, a number of Uzbek writers studied at the Institute of Literature and the Higher Literary Course in Moscow. Among them are Aziz Abdurazzoq, Jonrid Abdullakhanov, Murad Muhammad Dost, Togay Murad, Abdukakhhor Ibrohimov, Tora Mirzolar. As a result, the process of getting to know not only Russian literature, but also examples of European and American literature, their translation, and creative assimilation is accelerating. Another important aspect is that after the 60s of the XXth century, a new genre entered the literature. The impact of this innovation was first noticed in poetry by A.Oripov, E.Vohidov, O.Matjon, R.Parfi, and in prose by O.Yaqubov, P.Kadirov, Sh.Kholmirzaev, U.Nazarov, it ensured the emergence of new research in the works of O.Umarbekov, O.Mukhtar, and U.Hoshimov. E.A'zam, H.Sultan, M.M.Dust, T.Murod, who are considered to be the generation of the 80s, followed by N.Norqobilov, Sh.Botaev, S.Unar, A.Yuldosh, In the prose of N.Eshonqul,

Sh.Hamro, L.Borikhan, T.Rustamov, U.Hamdam, I.Sultans, the influence of world literature was clearly seen.

Among the listed writers, the tradition of being influenced by the works of four foreign writers is more obvious. These are works of: J. Joyce, W. Faulkner, G. G. Marquez, A. Camus.

References

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